

The Free Particle Schrodinger Equation and Constant Accelerating Frames

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In (1), a free quantum particle is analyzed from a frame moving such that $t_1=t$ (time) and $x_1=x-X(t)$. If $d/dt d/dt X(t)$ is not zero, then the frame is accelerating. It is found that the Schrodinger equation $i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ transforms into:

$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} W_1 = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx_1} \frac{d}{dx_1} W_1 + m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} x_1$ ((1)). If $dX/dt=\text{constant}$, the two equations are of the same form. If $d/dt d/dt X = a$ constant say g , the second equation is identical to one for a quantum particle moving in a gravitational field described by the potential mgx_1 . The physics of these two scenarios, however, is completely different. This implies that ((1)) should have two solutions. One should yield the free particle density, and the other the density of a particle in a gravitational field. It may be noted that in the case of a bound solution in the rest frame, the accelerating frame yields a solution with a time-dependent phase suggesting one is dealing with a moving frame scenario and not quantum physics for a gravitational field. The solution for the accelerating frame contains a term $\exp[i(p-dX/dt)x_1]$ with $dX/dt=f(t)$ so one follows the momentum as it changes in time. This, however, is a classical approach. In quantum mechanical bound states, acceleration is not displayed by momentum changing in time or space, but rather by a distribution of momenta $W(x)=\sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ changing in space.

Furthermore, from the correspondence principle, $\text{density}=C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity which decreases as a particle moves up in a gravitational field. Thus, classical density decreases and as this matches high energy quantum density, quantum density must also decrease. Thus, transforming the Schrodinger equation and seeking solutions of the form $\exp(i \text{phase}(x,t)) W(x,t)$ does not lead to a physical quantum solution of the transformed equation, but rather serves to pull out the transformation energy in order to regain the physical solution of a freely moving particle.

The Schrodinger equation for the gravitational field mgx may be solved to obtain a quantum solution involving Airy functions and a changing density as a second solution. Thus, the same Schrodinger equation has two different solutions describing very different physics.

Schrodinger Equation Transformation and Accelerating Frame

An accelerating frame is a non-inertial frame (e.g. a pendulum hangs at an angle not vertically), but one may still sit in such a frame and observe a rest frame with a quantum free particle described by the wavefunction $W(x,t) \exp(ipx-iEt)$ and Schrodinger equation: $i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ i.e.

$$t_1=t \quad \text{and} \quad x_1 = x - X(t) \quad ((2))$$

Following (1), the Schrodinger equation written in the new coordinates is:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W_1(x,t) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x,t) + m \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} X(t) x \quad ((3))$$

It may be noted that ((3)) is the equation of a quantum particle in a gravitational field if $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} X(x) = g$, yet the physics in the rest frame (a free particle) is completely different. If $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} X(t) = f(t)$, then the RHS of ((3)) does not represent kinetic plus potential energy. If $\frac{d}{dt} X(t) = a$ constant, then the form of the Schrodinger equation is the same in both frames, but there is no acceleration.

For $\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} X(t) = g$, it seems there should be two solutions to ((3)). One should preserve the density of the rest frame i.e. the free quantum particle. Thus, $W_1(x,t) = \exp(i \text{ phase}(x,t)) W(x,t)$ may be tried as a solution.

The basic idea seems to be to introduce a phase which acts under $i \frac{d}{dt}$ and $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ such that extra energy seen from the accelerating frame cancels. This is not really a quantum physics solution, but a math solution used to cancel unwanted effects of the accelerating frame. In particular, (1) suggests the solution:

$$W_1(x,t) = W(x,t) \exp\{-i [.5 m \int_0^t dt^2 \frac{dX}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} + m x \frac{dX}{dt}] \} \quad ((4))$$

The Integral term, when acted on by $\frac{d}{dt}$ partial yields the kinetic energy associated with the accelerating frame at t. $W(x,t) = \exp(ipx - iEt)$ where $E = \frac{p^2}{2m}$ i.e. the free particle energy.

$$((4)) \text{ may be rewritten as: } W(x,t) \exp[-i (p - m \frac{dX}{dt})] \exp(ip X(t)) \exp(-i \int) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{Then: } i \frac{d}{dt} W_1 = E + .5m \frac{dX}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} + m x \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} \quad \text{and} \\ -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 + m x \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} = m x \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dX}{dt} - \frac{1}{2m} (p - m \frac{dX}{dt})(p - m \frac{dX}{dt})$$

$W_1(x,t) = W(x,t) \exp(-i \text{ phase}(x,t))$ solves the Schrodinger equation of a particle in a gravitational field, but one must be careful of the physical interpretation. One retains the density of the original problem $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ as the density is physical and cannot change. One simply has an added phase which is somewhat curious. In ((5)) one sees the term: $p - m \frac{dX}{dt}$ where p (a number) is the momentum of the free particle and $m \frac{dX}{dt}$ the classical momentum of the accelerating frame. In quantum mechanics, one does not follow the acceleration of a particle in time, thus this expression is mathematical rather than quantum physics.

One may see this further by considering p and $-p$, i.e. two rest frame motions. Then, one has:

$$W_1 + W_2 = 2 \cos(px) \{ \exp(-i \int \text{ term}) \exp(-ix \frac{dX}{dt}) \} \quad ((6))$$

Thus, the bound state (in the rest frame) multiplied by a phase is obtained. This suggests the physics pertains to a bound state $\cos(px)$ in the rest frame with a phase shift representing effects of a frame measurement.

Correspondence Principle

To see that the solution ((4)) ((5)) is mathematical and related to removing unwanted frame effects, consider the correspondence principle which argues that in the high energy quantum limit, the classical density $C/v(x)$ where $.5m v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ matches the quantum density. Given that equation ((4)) represents a particle in a gravitational field, classical velocity should decrease with x and classical density and hence quantum density increase. Thus, one must have a quantum wavefunction $W_1(x,t)$ which increases with x and is not $W(x,t) \exp(-i \text{phase}(x,t))$. This is a physical wavefunction solution of ((3)), the Schrodinger equation for a particle in a gravitational field.

In (2), ((3)) the gravitational field Schrodinger equation is written as:

$d/dy d/dy W(y) = y W(y)$ ((7)) Here it is assumed that $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$.

And $y = k(x-E/mg)$, $k = \text{cube root}(2mmg)$ and with $W(x) = 1/k W(y)$.

The Airy functions $Ai(y)$ and $Bi(y)$ are solutions of ((7)) and are closely related to Bessel functions. One may see the height of these functions as well as their wavelength change with x .

Thus, one may explicitly solve the quantum problem of free fall and obtain a physical solution of ((3)).

As a result, it seems one should be careful when solving the time-dependent Schrodinger equation: $i\hbar d/dt (\text{partial}) W_1(x_1,t) = -1/2m d/dx_1 d/dx_1 W_1 + m x_1 g W_1$ ((3)). This equation appears to have at least two solutions. The first is $W_1(x,t) = \exp(-i\text{phase}(x_1,t)) W(x,t)$ where $W(x,t)$ is the free particle solution. Given that it is multiplied by a phase, the physics is that of a free particle with a phase representing unwanted effects of an accelerating frame. Given that the classical solution of a particle in a gravitational field involves a decreasing $v(x)$, classical density $C/v(x)$ must increase and this should be matched by decreasing quantum density according to the correspondence principle. Thus, there must be a second solution to ((3)) which allows for such a density change.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the time dependent Schrodinger equation may have multiple solutions and so one has to be careful of the physics involved. If one analyses a free quantum particle in a rest frame from an accelerating frame $t_1=t$ and $x_1=x-X(t)$ such that $d/dt dX/dt = g$, the free particle Hamiltonian transforms into a Hamiltonian for a particle in a gravitational field: $i\hbar d/dt (\text{partial}) W_1(x_1,t) = -1/2m d/dx_1 d/dx_1 W_1 + m x_1 dX/dt W_1$. Physically, this equation has a solution with a changing density $W_1^*W_1$ in accordance with the correspondence principle which states that classical density $C/v(x)$ changes with velocity $v(x)$ and matches high energy quantum density. For the case of the accelerating frame, however, the solution cannot change the free particle rest frame density W^*W , so the solution in the accelerating frame case should be

$W_1(x_1, t) = \exp(-i\text{phase}(x_1, t)) W$ with the phase being chosen to cancel out the extra energy effects of accelerating frame. One may see this further by superposing $W_1 + W_2$ i.e. frame solutions with p and $-p$. The result is $2\cos(px) \exp(-i\text{phase}_2(x, t))$. Thus, one obtains a bound state for the rest frame multiplied by a time dependent phase representing "frame" motion.

Thus, there are two solutions to the same Schrodinger equation, one mathematical representing the view of a free particle in a rest frame from a constant accelerating frame, and the second, a quantum physical solution of a particle in a gravitational field mgx with a changing density.

References

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